

Extension of Real Wave Quantum Mechanics to Three Dimensions

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Abstract

Real Wave Quantum Mechanics (RWQM) seeks to demonstrate that standard Quantum Mechanics (QM) can be derived from first principles based entirely on the interactions of real waves in an underlying universal medium. The concept of a 'point particle' is abandoned in favour of field structures which have distributed mass and angular momentum. The concept is similar to Schrödinger's original ideas which were subsequently abandoned in favour of the Born hypothesis. This paper extends previous work on 1 and 2 dimensional applications which used discrete linear/grid structures of entities known as Field Rotators (FRs). It is shown that FRs can be extended continuously in the 3rd dimension to give threadlike forms named FReds. Although continuous, it is shown that the 3rd dimension can be discretized to simplify calculations. Results are similar to those from Schrödinger's equation and can be viewed interactively. The meaning and role of phase in standard QM is made clear and intuitive by the RWQM approach.

1 Introduction

Real Wave Quantum Mechanics (RWQM) [Ewins(2021)], [Ewins(2022)] explains many puzzling features of QM and has been qualitatively successful in demonstrating stationary states for various potential fields in one and two dimensions. In particular, it is able to explain quantization of energy levels, rather than having them simply emerge from solution of the Schrödinger equation. Fully quantitative comparison is not yet possible because of the very large size of the calculations involved - the work so far has been with essentially 'toy' models of very limited scale.

An essential feature of RWQM are the entities referred to as Field Rotators (FRs) which arise where the phases of incoming waves are correlated (spin up) or anti-correlated (spin down) with the direction from which they arrive. This is essentially a 2 dimensional characteristic, whereas Schrödinger's equation appears to treat the three dimensions on an equivalent basis. Thus, extension of RWQM to 3 dimensions raises some interesting questions.

Figure 1: Effect of off-setting FR locations

In this paper various assumptions are evaluated and adopted. Calculations using the matrix method are carried out for a three dimensional Simple Harmonic Oscillator (SHO) potential field based on a cubic array of FRs truncated at radius 27. The results indicate that extension to 3D is feasible, and three dimensional structures akin to those of standard QM arise.

2 Calculation Considerations

It is not immediately obvious how Real Wave Quantum Mechanics might extend to three dimensions. The problems which must be addressed are as follows:

- **FR Orientation** - Do the spin vectors of all FRs within a 3D RWQM structure point in the same direction? Until there is any evidence to the contrary this is assumed to be the case.
- **Contributions in 3 Dimensions** - In 2 dimensions, the amplitude of the wave arriving at one FR from another is proportional to $1/r$, where r is the distance between them. This is because they share the same plane of rotation. In 3 dimensions (restricting our attention to the case where the rotation vectors point in the same direction), we must consider the case that planes of rotation are displaced as shown in Figure 1. The simplest assumption is probably that the outgoing wave amplitude from FR 2 varies as $\cos \theta$, where θ is the angle between its plane of rotation and the connecting line between the two FRs. When $\theta = 0$, the two FRs are in the same plane and there is no reduction in amplitude. When $\theta = \pm\pi/2$ the outgoing amplitude is reduced to zero. We must also consider the angle the incoming wave makes with the second FR. A similar assumption is made for the 'effectiveness' of the arriving wave - if it arrives in the plane of the second FR then it is fully effective, but the effectiveness reduces as $\cos \phi$. For parallel FRs, $\theta = \phi$, so the contribution from one FR to another varies as $\cos^2 \theta$.

- **The $x - y$ grid** - using a rectangular grid for FR locations in the $x - y$ plane seems like a reasonable extension from the 2 dimensional case but it begs the question of how it can be extended to encompass structures rotating around the central point ($m \neq 0$). In earlier work it was envisaged that such structures would contain 'necklaces' of FRs but these are incompatible with a rectangular grid. Work described in this paper is based on the rectangular $x - y$ form.
- **The Continuous z Coordinate** There seems to be no reason for FRs to be discrete in the third dimension. Consider for example, a 2-D eigenstructure in the x, y plane and place a similar structure an infinitesimal distance above it in the z direction. Apart from some amplitude change, which could be corrected for by perhaps halving the amplitude of each FR, the angles would hardly be affected, and the same eigenstructure would result. Adding further structures in infinitesimal steps leads to the picture of FRs being continuous rotating threads (perhaps FReds!) aligned with the z axis. However, once FReds become extended, interactions between various positions along them must be taken into account. How is this to be done? Work on this is described in the next section.

2.1 The z Coordinate

A program was written to calculate the discriminated¹ contributions from discrete z locations separated by the small distance Δz along one FRed, arriving at a single point on another FRed. The results are plotted as cumulative contributions from sources starting at $z = -400$ and moving to $z = 400$. This form illustrates that contributions from distant points cause the cumulative sum to 'go round in circles' as the source is moved along the z axis, whereas points near the target sum constructively.

Figure 2 shows the contributions at the origin received from a vertical FRed passing through the point $(3, 0)$. The amplitude scales with the number of points calculated, but the phase angle is remarkably consistent at -0.7266 .

Figure 3 shows the results for different separation distances with z in the range ± 400 and 10000 source points. The discriminated phase angle varies slightly with separation.

Finally, Table 1 shows the discriminated phase for an FR at the centre of a $300 \times 300 \times 300$ cube where the source points are separated as indicated along the z -axis. The discriminated phase is remarkably close to $\pi/2$. It may be recalled [Ewins(2021)] that a similar test for a 2 dimensional grid gave a discriminated phase which was very close to $\pi/4$.

¹The notion of discrimination is described in detail in [Ewins(2021)]. In essence, discrimination takes the amplitude and phase of all waves passing through a point and weights them according to the extent to which their phase and arriving direction are correlated or anti-correlated (Phase-Direction Correlation, PDC). The result is a complex number representing the phase and amplitude of an FR which would be formed at this point (or the contribution to be added to the FR which is already present). Spin is indicated by whether it is a correlation or anti-correlation.

Figure 2: Cumulative Discriminated Contributions for FReds 3 units apart with stated number of points over z range ± 400

Figure 3: Cumulative Discriminated Contributions for FReds various distances apart with 10000 points over z range ± 400

The scaling factor for continuous FReds is essentially irrelevant, since it will be absorbed into the reaction coefficient α . The constancy of the phase angle results from some underlying geometric feature and opens up the opportunity for continuous FReds to be approximated by discrete FRs at integer positions along the Z axis. However, such an approximation is likely to suffer if the ψ values vary too quickly relative to the FR separation. Unfortunately this is exactly the situation which arises when using very small toy models as required for the matrix eigenvalue method, which puts a limit on what can be expected.

3 Results for 3-D SHO Potential

With the proviso that we cannot expect too much from a toy model with a questionable simplifying assumption, application of the matrix method has been attempted. It has proved possible with available computing resources to per-

Table 1: Discriminated Phase at Origin for $300 \times 300 \times 300$ Cube with Various Δz Values

Δz	Discriminated Angle at Origin
1/100	-1.56568
1/50	-1.56568
1/20	-1.56568
1/10	-1.56569
1/5	-1.56570
1/2	-1.56575
1	-1.56145

Figure 4: Eigenvalues for First 20 3D Structures

form calculations for a sphere of radius 27. Memory is a limiting factor, and precision has been reduced from complex128 to complex64 to achieve this radius. Calculation times have precluded attempts to optimize the F_R matrix to be unitary so that the reduction in rotation rate (energy) can be measured, as it was for the 2D case. Nevertheless, the method gives sensible eigenstructures and eigenvalues. The SHO spring constant used is 0.003 which is relatively high in order to constrain the structure within the limited radius. α is the usual whimsical $1/137$.

3.1 Eigenvalues

Figure 4 shows the eigenvalues for the first 20 eigenstructures. The degeneracy pattern is present although it is not as clearly defined as for the 2D work. The expected QM result would be degeneracy groups containing 1, 3, 6, 10 eigenstates with energies of $3\hbar/2, 5\hbar/2, 7\hbar/2, 9\hbar/2$ respectively.

3.2 Structure 1

Visualization of 3-D orbital structures is a problem here (as it is for standard quantum mechanics). Results of this work have been processed as interactive HTML files stored separately on Zenodo. These enable the structure to be scaled and rotated. They should be accessible on most devices².

- Structure 1
- Structure 2
- Structure 3
- Structure 4
- Structure 5
- Structure 6
- Structure 7
- Structure 8
- Structure 9
- Structure 10

The method used is to represent the squared magnitude of each FR by the size of the point plotted, and the phase at each point (up to a phase factor) by the colour of the point, using a cyclic colour map. Phases have been processed to remove the phase alternation. This enables phase differences between lobes to be clearly identified.

Structure 1 is essentially spherical, corresponding to an 's' solution to the Schrödinger equation in a central potential. In fact, there is a small degree of oblateness which is better illustrated in Figure 5, which shows cross sections in the $x-y$, $x-z$ and $y-z$ planes passing through the origin. (Although the usual phase arrows are shown, it should be remembered that the rotation is only in the $x-y$ plane for all three diagrams.) Figures 5b and 5c show a small degree of oblateness compared with the circular form of Figure 5a. However, given the small size of the toy and the large value used for the discretization of z , the form is remarkably spherical.

Figure 6 shows the variation of phase along the z axis. As usual, phases alternate by approximately π between adjacent FRs. This alternation is continuous along all three axes (only the z axis is illustrated in Figure 6).

The phase alternation masks that there is a smooth variation in phase occurring along the axes. This is apparent in the interactive figure, but is better seen in Figure 7 which shows the result of removing the alternation and adjusting

²Click on the structure number to be taken to the Zenodo site and download. Once downloaded launch in your browser. Use the mouse wheel to zoom in and out, and drag to rotate.

Figure 5: Axial Slices of s Orbital

Figure 6: Variation of FR phase along axis

Figure 7: Variation of FR phase along the axes after correcting for alternation.

by appropriate factors of 2π . The x and y phase variations are identical but the z phase variation diverges slightly. This change in phase across a structure was noted and discussed for the 2D case in [Ewins(2022)]. For a stationary state such as this, the Schrödinger equation would predict the same phase at all points at each instant of time, but here we have an additional fixed internal phase structure.

3.3 Structure 2

The second structure is best visualized in the interactive Figure. Figure 8 is included for completeness. It is symmetrical around the z axis and has the 'hour glass' shape of the $n = 2, l = 1, m = 0$ orbital of the H atom, but compressed by the different potential form.

(a) $x - y$

(b) $x - z$

(c) $y - z$

Figure 8: Axial Slices of Structure 2

The interactive figure shows most clearly that the phases of the two lobes are different. This is also illustrated in Figure 9 which shows the phase of the

Figure 9: Variation of FR phase along the z axis for structure 2

FRs along the z axis. Although this is superficially similar to Figure 6, closer examination reveals that opposite locations on the z axis have phases differing by approximately π . (For example, the phase at $z = -20$ is low, while at $z = +20$ it is high.) In explanations of the Schrödinger results for the hydrogen atom the phase difference between the lobes is usually noted as a 'mathematical' thing since there is no clear understanding of what phase 'is'. Here, the FR phase difference between the two lobes gives a very simple explanation for the shape of the structure: every point on the $x - y$ plane is receiving contributions from the FRs in the $z > 0$ lobe which are exactly cancelled out by those of opposite phase from FRs with $z < 0$. Hence FRs on the $x - y$ plane must have zero magnitude.

Figure 10 shows how the phase varies along the z axis once alternation has been removed. The phase difference between the two lobes shows up as a step change at the origin. As for the first structure, Figure 10 and the interactive Figure show the presence of an internal phase structure which is not predicted by the Schrödinger equation.

3.4 Structures 3 and 4

Axial slices of structures 3 and 4 are shown in Figures 11 and 12 respectively. These are also hourglass shaped lying almost (but not quite) along the x and y axes. They are symmetrical above and below the $x - y$ plane but seem to be slightly asymmetric about the line joining the two maxima.

Figures 13 and 14 show the alternating phases along the axes passing predominantly through the hour glasses for structures 3 and 4. Once again, the two lobes are out of phase, although the slight asymmetry is apparent.

Apart from the asymmetry, structures 2, 3 and 4 are similar to Schrödinger's prediction of three orthogonal hour glasses, which is remarkable. Schrödinger's equation is symmetric with respect to the three axes and as it is being applied to a central potential the three hour glass structures must be identical. RWQM requires a unique plane of rotation for the FRs so structure 2 is easily under-

Figure 10: Variation of FR phase along the z axis for structure 2 after correcting for alternation.

Figure 11: Axial Slices of Structure 3

stood, as it lies perpendicular to this plane. The formation of two orthogonal hour glasses in the $x - y$ plane is harder to understand. Their shape is consistent in one sense: consider for example the hour glass along the x -axis. Every point on the $y - z$ plane will receive contributions of equal magnitude but opposite phase from every FR within the structure so this must be a nodal plane. However, the four lobes (two for each structure) in the $x - y$ plane represent a breaking of the rotational symmetry. Perhaps the correct RWQM solutions are the two rotational states ($m = \pm 1$), and the states found are superposition of these - in the same way that chemists present rotational orbitals as real by superimposing the opposite rotational states. What rotational states 'are' in RWQM is a work in progress. In any case, it appears that the matrix method is not suited to finding them. This could explain why structures 3 and 4 are 'odd'.

Figure 12: Axial Slices of Structure 4

Figure 13: Variation of FR phase along the y axis for structure 3

3.5 Higher Structures

Higher structures ($n=3$) are illustrated in the interactive Figures. They correspond to those of the hydrogen atom to some extent, but of course, this is a different central potential. They share the features of the $n=1$ and 2 structures, with lobes having differing phases and internal phase structures within the lobes. Structures which would be expected to contain internal rotation continue to be identified in 'chemist's' format. They are all beautiful!

4 Conclusions

This paper set out to address the question of how an apparently 2D theory involving entities (FRs) rotating in a plane, could give rise to something like the Schrödinger equation, which seems to treat the 3 dimensions on an equal footing. The main conclusions are:

Figure 14: Variation of FR phase along the x axis for structure 4

- planar FRs can be extended in the third dimension as filaments (called FReds).
- FReds can be represent by discretized FRs along the z axis.
- the phase of discriminated contributions to a point on one FRed from the whole of another FRed is not sensitive to the z discretization.
- for a cubic array of FReds with discretized z values, the phase of the discriminated contributions to a central FR seems to be approximately $\pi/2$. (This can be compared with a similar result for a planar array which gave contributions at an angle of $\pi/4$.) [Ewins(2021)]
- results obtained from unit discretization of the z axis by the matrix method are closely related to the Schrödinger results.

It should be noted that when Schrödinger's equation is applied to 3D situations with central potential, the results are always rotationally symmetric about the z axis, so one plane is being picked out in an arbitrary fashion. RWQM picks out one plane because it is the spin plane of the FRs (or FReds) which is envisaged to be a real feature the structure. The fact that the same 3D 'orbitals' seem to be predicted by either theory is quite remarkable. However, further work must explore how rotational motion fits into the theory. Previous ideas in terms of 'necklaces' of FRs [Ewins(2021)] now seem to be problematic.

References

- [Ewins(2021)] Ron Ewins. Self interacting wave fields - a physical wave basis for quantum mechanics, 2021. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807650>.

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